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A STRUCTURED DIGITAL OFFER FOR DEVELOPING LEARNING STRATEGIES AS ADD-ON FOR HIGHER EDUCATION ENGINEERING CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Early entry age of university students, little self-learning experience and courses with several hundred students: bachelor students are often poorly prepared for university requirements. Since individual support for first-year students is hardly possible with student numbers that have been rising for years, the course design is adapted by putting weight on highly structured teaching-learning arrangements, clearly restricted learning objectives, and narrowly defined examination content. However, the techniques for self-organized acquisition of knowledge, which allow for an individual holistic approach to learning are neglected. As a result, learning content is often memorized rather than absorbed - and thus forgotten again a few weeks or even days after the exam, leaving the "learner" with a lack of both, expertise and the skills necessary to acquire it. In 2020 we set out to enable young students to experiment with learning strategies without coaching them individually. A podcast series and short e-exams were developed and didactically embedded in a basic cross-sectional course for around 160 students. The evaluation showed great acceptance and appreciation from the students' side for the intervention. They experienced themselves as effective learners while picking up learning strategies seemingly in passing.

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1 INTRODUCTION

When students enroll at university, they come with at least 12 years' experience with learning in formalized settings. However, many find themselves unprepared for what their new intellectual surroundings expect from them regarding learning strategies and learning behavior. This often results in students experiencing immense psychological stress (which hinders learning progress) and developing a grade-oriented rather than content-oriented learning behavior for the sake of passing courses, thus falling short of their capabilities and even dropping out.

The maxim to prepare young people for the labor market in an ever-shorter period, requires highly efficient, standardized processes of teaching and learning. The techniques for self-organized acquisition of knowledge, which are necessary for lifelong learning, have no place in such a schooling concept. However, self-regulated learning and its according learning strategies are still a basic requirement of higher education. As a common helpless reaction, university staff often expresses the attitude that simply not everyone is personally qualified to study at university and young students quitting is, therefore, a logical consequence of selection. However, this "consequence" results in a loss of possibly very capable young people for the scientific or professional field, as well as in reduced performance of a large part of the remaining group. Others have put a lot of effort into active learning approaches, trying to offer their students self-learning experiences e.g. by demanding project-based learning. However, those formats usually require basic knowledge and are thus designed for higher semesters, which means that those students who probably need such learning opportunities most, might have given up before getting there.

Of course, there are books and introductory training courses on how to study that are recommended frequently by teaching staff. However, young students who already feel overwhelmed by the sheer amount of compulsory coursework will not invest their scarce capacities for supplementary activities. A much more promising approach would be, to integrate learning experiences that foster new competencies into basic compulsory courses in such a way that students can immediately experience the usefulness of changes in their learning behavior. This was also our starting point at the Department of Industrial Information Technology at Technische Universität Berlin when we set out to develop a digital teaching-learning arrangement that enables young students to experience self-efficacy with learning strategies while actually doing basic coursework. The product is a didactic concept that includes a podcast series and self-examination quizzes in careful timing with the weekly lectures. In the following section, we discuss didactic and psychological basics upon which we developed our concept. Afterwards we present the didactic concept and its implementation before describing the evaluation and discussing the results.

2 STATE OF THE ART

While learning is common to all living beings, humans are distinct by their capability to reflect upon their own learning process and thus develop strategies for efficient learning behavior. When high school graduates enter universities they are already equipped with numerous such learning strategies specific for the school setting. Helpful as those might have been for mastering school, they are often not sufficient or even obstructive to meet learning expectations at university level [1]. According to Schiefele and Wild [2] learning at university requires

- (1) cognitive learning strategies (e. g. repetition strategies, organizational strategies, elaboration strategies and critical thinking),
- (2) metacognitive learning strategies (e. g. planning learning activities, assessing learning activities and regulating learning activities), and
- (3) strategies for using internal and external resources (e. g. directing attention and effort, organizing the learning environment and forming learning partnerships).

To develop those strategies, a rather sophisticated understanding of knowledge is required. However, in young students' experience, learning success is bound primarily to learning strategies of simple memorization. This comes from having studied so far with the strongly simplified representations of reality found in school books targeting dualistic assessment of learning outcomes via school exams. Furthermore, high school students are used to a setting where they are told what exactly they are expected to learn or rather memorize [3]. The entire process of selecting and organizing information oneself plays a subordinate role at school but is a required basic competence at university.

2.1 Self-directed learning

Many researchers involved in university teaching emphasize the need to help students to overcome obstructive ideas of knowledge and learning right in their first year as a major condition for them to succeed in their studies [1], [3], [4]. Self-directed learning is the first out of five readiness dimensions of students defined by [5]. It classically includes taking on responsibility to understand own learning needs, establishing learning goals and implementing learning strategies and evaluation [6].

From a psychological perspective, self-regulation includes control of cognitive, metacognitive, volitional and behavioral acts to monitor and assess the own learning process [7]. Learning, in general, is a highly constructive process on the side of the learners who have to create complex neuronal networks and establish cognitive representations of the learning subject to transform external information into internally knit-in knowledge. The more cognitive representations and the more neuronal connections already exist, the easier learners find it to integrate new information and put it into relation with what is already there, e.g. learn more. Learners that are inexperienced in a field, however, do not have many representations yet that would help them to file new fragments of knowledge into existing concepts. They must look at and make sense of each fragment singularly

before tentatively putting it somewhere until something else might come up that they can probably put it into some kind of relation with.

2.2 Memory and cognitive representations

The basis for many psychological memory models today, although thoroughly adapted, is the multi-store model by [8]. The authors claim the brain to have three different storages, (1) sensory register, (2) short-term storage, and (3) long-term storage. The sensory register represents visual and acoustic impulses as pictures or sounds for few seconds. If those appear irrelevant, we forget them immediately. The long-term storage is where information is stored for an indefinite time, provided, the short-term storage has processed the information thoroughly. In later models, short-term storage and sensory register are both integrated in the instantiation “working memory”. The working memory does all major cognitive work. It is responsible for both, assessing new information and recovering information from the long-term storage to interpret situations or find solutions.

According to the “Levels of Processing model” the representation (memory) in the long-term storage gets stronger and more accessible with duration and intensity of an information’s processing by the working memory. This means the more often and intensely learners make use of an information they have acquired by applying it in different contexts, and thus making connections to other information, the stronger a cognitive representation will they build. Transferring the model back into didactics, we find definitions of “deep” and “surface” approaches to learning [9]. Deep approaches thus refer to e.g. consciously relating ideas to previous knowledge and experience and looking for underlying principles. Surface approaches, on the other hand, are characterized by e.g. treating the course as unrelated bits of knowledge and memorizing facts.

Effective learning techniques mirror those findings. Repetition, for example, makes use of the spacing effect [10], meaning that memory performance is higher when splitting the learning time allocated to an information piece into several shorter slots distributed over time. This effect is explained among others by the “Encoding Variability Theory”, which states that over time a bigger variety of context referring to a specific information can be stored, which makes it easier for a person to retrieve the information. Also according to the “Study-Phase Retrieval Theory” the mental traces, which can be seen as guiding paths towards a specific representation, are strengthened every time they are activated, e.g. the representation is retrieved. Both theories have been shown to be significant for the “lag effect” [11], which is the positive effect of longer pauses in between retrieval of an information on the learning outcome. It is important to notice that the lag effect’s function follows an U-shape. Thus, while it can be considered useful to let some time pass in between first encounter and first retrieval of an information, the positive effect wears off after a while. A pause of one to two weeks seems to be optimal as suggested by research.

2.3 Understanding the own learning needs

Learners can increase their memory performance even more by checking the quality of the representation they are recalling during repetition via feedback [12]. Feedback is utterly important to young students since they usually lack the ability to judge their own competency within the new field [13]. E.g. well-presented lectures that take seemingly little cognitive effort to follow, mislead students to believe that they have learned a lot while listening, although the content can actually not be stored in the long-term storage if there are yet too few cognitive representations to integrate the new information and if it is not repeatedly revised. This negative correlation hinders students' active engagement and taking on responsibility for their own learning processes. One could say, only when learners must try to make sense out of things themselves will they start to realize their lack of understanding. Feedback can help them realize that they have been misled.

2.4 Active engagement in passive learning arrangements

Deep learning strategies are often associated with students' active engagement. "Active" as an operationalized term is defined as opposed to "passive" formats; the latter foremost refers to classical lectures. Nevertheless, students can cognitively engage actively also in passive formats, foremost by active listening. Active listening requires effort and skill and is the precondition for integrating lecture content into the own cognitive representations [9]. Since top students show strong cognitive, affective and psycho-motor active listening skills [14] it is a predictor for learning success. Helping students develop that skill becomes even more important since distractive stimuli have become omnipresent with digitalization [15]. Students who might have mastered school teachers' lectures by day-dreaming are now allowed to bring electronic devices to the lecture room that connect them to the entire digital world. Thus they need to develop the skill to keep up following the person standing several meters away while being exposed to constant competing stimuli right before their noses.

In summary, university students often arrive at their new learning surroundings with school-related concepts of learning that are obstructive to mastering higher education. They lack basic competencies regarding self-regulated learning, which are necessary to build up professional expertise through cognitive representations and associative networks as well as for life-long learning in less structured learning environments. They need learning experiences that help them challenge former concepts and establish a deep approach to learning by actively engaging with course content. They need to identify lacks of knowledge as well as ineffective learning routines in order to take over responsibility for their learning process.

3 CONCEPT FOR INTEGRATING LEARNING EXPERIENCES

Based on the ideas above we decided to develop a didactic concept and materials for one of our cross-sectional bachelor courses that should help our students make valuable learning experiences and develop effective studying routines. The cross-

sectional nature of the course seemed particularly suitable since it requires our students to connect knowledge from different engineering fields, thus building up complex representations.

The didactic goals of the concept were to give students the chance to

1. build up basic concepts before listening to the lecture to experience that preparing oneself helps following the lecture and thus makes attending it more effective
2. check how much they have learned directly after listening to a set of information to realize that listening is not automatically learning and develop active listening skills
3. continuously learn throughout the semester instead of shortly before the examination to experience the effect of distributed learning over time and of giving the brain the chance to shift information to the long-term storage.

Regarding scarce staffing we decided to go for a digital solution for our approx. 160 students. We did not want to change the lecture itself, which had just undergone thorough revision. Therefore, we needed a concept that could be integrated as add-on. In accordance with goal 1, we had to provide our students supplementary information before the lecture in a way that they would actually use it. Thus, we decided to offer bonus points for using it. Also for motivational reasons we decided to go for a podcast, featuring a young lively teacher that was on good terms with our students, interviewing experts for the upcoming lecture topics in each episode. We planned the interviews to have an unofficial note to them, taking care to use first names only and use simple language. The episodes should loosely introduce basic concepts of the corresponding topic, its importance in practice, and current trends in the field.

Fig. 1 Structure of the weekly lecture, podcast episodes and quizzes

In order to allow our students to realize that while listening they might not actually have been listening (goal 2) we added an online quiz to each episode. Students would only receive the bonus points if they scored 100 % with no more than two attempts. Since they were able to listen to the podcast episodes as often as they wished, this was achievable. We planned to release each episode and quiz on our learning management platform one week before the corresponding lecture, and close it again the moment the lecture began

Fig. 1), so that the students could benefit noticeably and immediately from the preparation effect during the lecture.

The lecture would recall many of the cognitive representations that the students had yet already built up. By reactivating those representations few days after first encounter in slightly different contexts they should be strengthened due to encoding variability theory and study-phase retrieval theory. In practice, our students should make the experience that they had better access to what they had learned. This would also nourish the learning experience that recalling what they had actively learned all semester long by considering, repeating, and integrating it into their own constantly growing cognitive representation of the subject, was much easier than trying to memorize mere facts in big number shortly before the exam (goal 3). To help our students feel the difference between applying the techniques we offered and not doing so, we only released every second podcast, letting every other lecture stand for itself.

4 IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

The course we chose was "Fundamentals of Industrial Information Technology", which covers the basics of information technology and the use of respective tools. The module consists of an exercise in the form of tutorials and guided project work as well as the lecture, which we intended to enrich with our new didactic concept.

We created the podcast episodes gradually over the course of 2020, winning experts for the topics from among our scientific colleagues at our department and our partner institute Fraunhofer IPK. The interviews were initially recorded in the professional recording studio and assisted by technical experts at TU Berlin. Due to Covid-19 restrictions, we had to switch to online recordings via ZOOM later.

To avoid contradictions between podcast and lecture, we revisited the lecture slides together with the according expert. We then together developed a loose script to which the interviewer and the expert could adhere during the interview. The focus was on introducing the general lecture topic by providing hands-on application examples. For this, we first needed to develop a common understanding of the key aspects with our expert partners. Since the podcast was designed as first encounter with the respective topics for our students, contradictory aspects were avoided. We also pre-phrased complicated issues in simple language together with our expert partners.

After an interview had been produced, it was time for the quiz to be developed. For this, a didactic expert tutor once again compared podcast and lecture content and also considered structure and content of the module's main exam to make sure the quiz would refer to all those elements. The quizzes contained about ten multiple choice and multiple answer questions for each podcast episode. There was no time limit when taking the quiz so that students could even interrupt the quiz to check the podcast once more. After finishing the quiz, the students received automatic feedback on which items they had answered incorrectly, without providing the correct answer, and were offered a second go, which they could take right away or later

during the week. After the second attempt, they again received their feedback and the quiz was closed for them. Students could access both, podcast and quiz, freely during the week before the related lecture.

To evaluate the success of our concept we checked the usage statistics and administered a short feedback survey on our concept to our students in the end of the semester. We asked them how many episodes and quizzes they had worked with, how they liked the format and how much it had helped them. Since we also wanted to measure if the concept had a side-effect on the students' learning outcome we assessed their scoring in the main exam, comparing answers for which they had, according to their own statement, prepared themselves using podcast and quizzes with those for which they had not.

5 RESULTS

We had not considered spontaneous responses from our students in our evaluation plan since we did not expect to get too much. Nevertheless, we could gain interesting feedback in this regard. Unsolicited emails kept coming in to the teaching team praising the podcasts as a great teaching format and actually thanking us for the production. This was something we had never experienced before. Looking at the usage statistics, 86 % of our 159 students had listened to all of the podcasts, and 14 % had listened to at least some, which was unsurprising due to the bonus system. In addition to this initial incentive, however, students quickly took a personal liking to the offering. In the survey, 81 % of the 159 students said they would have listened to at least some of the podcasts even if there had been no bonus points for doing so (Fig. 2). For the quizzes, however, only 62 % said this. In addition, 56 % of respondents rated the podcasts as "really good" and 38 % as "mostly good" in response to the question of how much they liked them. Only 6 % of students rated the podcasts as mediocre or indicated that they rather disliked them. The worst category "not at all" was selected not once.

Fig. 2 Students' answer to "Would you have used ... without bonus points?", n=159

Fig. 3 Students' answer to "How well could you follow the lecture ...", n=159

We asked the students how well they had been able to follow each lecture, depending on whether they had prepared for it or not. The comparison showed that 80% of the students who had worked with the podcasts and quizzes were able to follow the corresponding lecture "very well" or "mainly well", while this was only true for 54% of lectures that had not been prepared accordingly (Fig. 3). However, comparing the results from the major exam no differences showed between neither intra- nor interpersonal comparison of scoring in sections for which the students had used podcast and quizzes and those for which they had not. The average grade even decreased from 2,97 to 3,30. However, grades of this semester are difficult to compare to former semesters, given that this was a challenging time for both students and teaching staff alike, being the first "digital semester" to be held remote under the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic regulations.

With 68 %, the majority of students was satisfied with the limited availability of the podcasts in the week before the corresponding lecture. This was the most frequently selected response option to the question of when the podcasts should be released, although a good third of the students also stated that they would like to be able to work on the set after the lecture. When asked about their preferred media format, 56 % of the students rated the podcast format as better than video interviews or as equal to them. 39 %, on the other hand, would have preferred video interviews.

6 DISCUSSION

To evaluate knowledge and changes in students' mindset is very difficult. We expect distorting effects due to our decision to offer bonus points, for example. We are not able to tell if our students would really have used the podcasts and quizzes without the incentive but we believe that such incentives are necessary at least until the students had a chance to realize the benefits they gain from preparing and revising apart from the bonus points. We interpret our students proclamation that they will use the format even without bonus points as indicator for the effectiveness of the concept. Also the unusual act of sending us compliments and notes of thanks in our opinion shows that our concept addresses a sensitive spot.

Our concept did not include students' guided reflection on learning experiences, which is considered a necessity for self-regulation in learning [16]. Our focus was on creating a learning situation in which our students got the chance to compare different approaches to learning as spontaneous personal reaction to their immediate experiences, without someone telling them to do so. We expected a certain degree of resistance in some of our students if we would give them additional tasks that were not obviously related to course content. This was the reason why we carefully designed the learning experience to be integrated into the coursework as unobtrusively as possible. However, it might very well be that asking students explicitly to reflect upon their attitudes, actions and results would further strengthen the effects of the intervention.

Our students did not score higher in the exam due to the concept. This is no surprise since learners invest their resources when they do not feel prepared enough for

examination by the coursework. In our case, they already invested extra time in repeatedly listening to the podcast and doing the quizzes, usually scoring 100 % at the second attempt, thus feeling well prepared and allocating their energy to other fields, e.g. the lectures for which no additional material had been offered. However, we did not target high scores but wanted to tackle our students' concept of learning. We are aware that a few months of doing things differently can probably not weigh out 13 years of former experience. However, if our students feel that their school-based learning strategies are of limited use in the university setting, they now have already experimented with an alternative approach to learning.

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